

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF HUMOR IN POLITICAL DISCOURSE

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Annotation. *The article examines the linguistic features of humor in political discourse. It analyzes the techniques and methods of creating humor in political discourse, which are necessary for creating a certain image of a politician. Some means of creating humor in political speech are considered - language play or pun, zeugma, irony, occasionalisms, chiasmus and paradox.*

Key words: *linguistic features, creating humor, political speech, language play, pun, zeugma, irony, occasion-alisms, chiasmus, paradox, political discourse.*

Аннотация: *в статье рассматриваются языковые особенности юмора в политическом дискурсе. В нем анализируются приемы и способы создания юмора в политическом дискурсе, необходимые для создания определенного имиджа политического деятеля. Рассмотрены некоторые средства создания юмора в политической речи – языковая игра или каламбур, зевгма, ирония, окказионализмы, хиазм и парадокс.*

Ключевые слова: *языковые особенности, создания юмора, политическая речь, языковая игра, каламбур, зевгма, ирония, окказионализмы, хиазм, парадокс, политический дискурс.*

Annotatsiya: *maqolada siyosiy nutqdagi yumorning lingvistik xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Unda siyosat arbo-bining ma'lum qiyofasini yaratish uchun zarur bo'lgan siyosiy nutqda yumor yaratish uslublari tahlil qilinadi. Siyosiy nutqda yumor yaratishning ba'zi vositalari ko'rib chiqiladi: til o'yinlari yoki so'z o'yinlari, zeugma, ironiya, kazarizm, xiazmus va paradoks kabi vositalar ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *lingvistik xususiyatlar, yumor yaratish, siyosiy nutq, til o'yinlari, so'z o'yini, zeugma, ironiya, okka-zializm, xiazm, paradoks, siyosiy nutq.*

Recently, the problem of humor in political discourse has become one of the most attractive areas of re-search. The problem of political humor seems to be relevant at the present time. Every politician uses humor in his speeches, not only to add expressiveness and emotionality to his statements, but also to maintain his political image. Political image is one of the most important components of a politician's program, so politicians consciously use only those funny statements that can positively influence his image. Political humor is a specific characteristic of the linguistic personality of a politician. This is one of the ways to bring a representative of power closer to the people, to make a politician accessible and his speech more understandable and attractive to the masses.

Political humor emphasizes the features of a politician not only as a political personality, but also as a linguistic one. The researchers focused on the statements of politicians that create a comic effect: jokes during speeches, mistakes that cause laughter, the creation of puns during political speeches.

Many politicians, creating a joke, put a certain sub-text into it. Sometimes a politician can describe the entire current situation, relieve tension in negotiations or characterize an opponent with one joke. The suddenness of the transition from official political speech to everyday speech enhances the comic effect of the statement. At the same time, it should be taken into account that any joke by a representative of a particular ethnic group, intended for a compatriot, is based on the corresponding background knowledge. Therefore, transferring it into another language, counting on a foreign speaker, presents significant difficulties.

This is what causes difficulties in intercultural communication. In this regard, the study of political humor in multilingual discourses seems quite relevant. It should be remembered that communication in which humor is created can occur at a high political level, which significantly increases the importance of communication. The political image of a politician is directly related to humor in political discourse. Politicians consciously use humor to maintain their authority. After all, it will subsequently become the main weapon in the struggle for power.

To create humor in political discourse, language play or puns can be used, as well as various stylistic devices: irony, zeugma, paradox, chiasmus and occasionalisms. Language play is one of the means of creating humor in a politician's speech. It releases enormous expressive potential inherent in language, and this is why politicians so willingly use it. The purpose of language play is to attract the attention of the listener with the help of a linguistic joke, humor, wit. Language games are based on various linguistic phenomena. Thus, puns are created with the help of homonyms. Occasionalisms are widely used. Paronomasia is also a popular element of language games. Allusions and paradoxes are involved in language games, which are designed to lead to a radical change in the content plan with a slight transformation of the expression plan. Language games are designed for the background knowledge of the addressee. Otherwise, the author faces communicative failure. A pun is often created on the basis of the polysemy of words, which makes polysemy one of the most expressive means of creating a pun. In their speeches, politicians often use this technique for expressiveness.

Metaphorization in a pun is one of the most economical and expressive ways of revealing the content of a thought and conveying one's attitude, assessment to what is being said. In a metaphor, along with a figurative meaning, there is an additional or figurative connotation. Connotation reflects an evaluative, emotional or stylistic coloring, means something other than what lies on the surface, contains a subtext, a hidden meaning. Metaphor, itself, being a language game, is the basis of witty puns.

The function of zeugma is to create a comic effect. Zeugma not only contrasts words with different semantics, which causes a comic effect, but also connects words that are heterogeneous in meaning, which often leads to mutual influence, revealing deep meanings. Thus, the main means of expression underlying zeugma is polysemy.

Politicians often use the stylistic device of irony in their speeches. Irony is a stylistic device by means of which an interaction of two types of lexical meanings appears in a word: subject-logical and contextual, based on the relationship of opposition (contradiction). Thus, these two meanings are actually mutually exclusive. The device is often implemented in colloquial speech.

Among the main distinguishing features, one can single out an unjustified reduction or exaggeration of the properties of an object, phenomenon or proper name, which creates a contrast between the new (elevated or debased) name and the denotate. Such a contrast is the basis of sharply expressed irony. The mechanism of action of the technique of ironic

exaggeration and deliberate reduction lies in the deliberate strengthening (weakening) of the properties, features, characteristics of objects, phenomena that express the absurdity of the statement. Another technique for creating humor in political discourse is chiasmus. Chiasmus is a figure of speech or, more precisely, a technique for enhancing expressiveness by mirroring the arrangement of two adjacent combinations, words or sentences. It can also be said that chiasmus is a figure of speech consisting of a reverse "cross-shaped" arrangement of the elements of two combinations united by a common member. This is a noticeable, bright, interesting technique, quite often encountered in humor. This technique is used to enhance expressiveness by mirroring two adjacent combinations of words or sentences.

So, some means of creating humor in political speech are considered - language play or pun, zeugma, irony, occasionalisms, chiasmus and paradox. All these means are an integral part of the language game. They are used unexpectedly, take the listener by surprise, amaze with their unpredictability. The humor of political discourse is a little-studied phenomenon in intercultural communication. But, despite this, the problem of political humor in intercultural communication is the most interesting topic for many researchers. It should be noted that in communication, political humor can cause difficulties in understanding, since the concept of funny differs in different cultures. Many questions arise about preserving cultural coloring in the statements of politicians. The need to preserve it in intercultural communication is an important problem.

In conclusion of the characteristics of the methods of increasing the effectiveness of intercultural communication in the format of political discourse, it should be said that when conveying political humor in intercultural communication, it is necessary to take into account the authority of the speaker and, for reasons of political correctness, not allow the translation of jokes or humorous statements to the opponent, since this can be perceived as an insult. When conveying political humor, it is important to convey the subtext intended by the author, its emotional and informational side, but at the same time be very careful, since an incorrect interpretation of the joke can cause disapproval from foreign listeners.

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